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Chemical Examination of *Lantana camara* Linn.

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LANTANA CAMARA Linn (N.O. Verbenaceae) causes severe photosensitisation during fruiting and flowering stages¹ and icterus in sheep. The leaves of the plant were extensively examined and isolated the triterpenes lantadene A, lantadene B^{2,3,4}, lantalic acid, lactic acid and 3-Keto ursolic acid⁵⁻⁸ and an unidentified ketosteroid lancamarone⁹.

In the present investigation the roots of the plant were examined. The root powder was extracted with hot EtOH and the extract on removal of the solvent gave a dark greenish brown residue (3%). The residue was fractionated into Et₂O (2%) and H₂O (1%) solubles. (The aqueous extract gave yellow colour with alkali and blue colour with acid). The Et₂O extract was fractionated into neutral (0.1% waxes) and acidic (1.9%) fractions by extraction with 5% NaOH. TLC on silica gel G indicated that the acid is a mixture of three or four compounds. One was separated and purified by fractional crystallisation from EtOH and chromatography over silica gel and identified as oleanolic acid (1.5%) C, 98.72; H, 10.81. C₃₀H₄₈O₃ requires C, 98.95 and H, 10.53%. (C, 1.2 in CHCl₃): m.p. 290°-92°: [α]_D+80°, I.R. 1665 cm⁻¹, 825 cm⁻¹: NMR spectra multiplet centered at 4.7τ (IH) for trisubstituted double bond: Prominent MS: right-half ratio Diels-Alder fragment m/e 248, m/e 233 (248-CH₃) and m/e 189 (233-CO₂): comparison of the acetate with authentic oleanolic acid acetate (m.m.p. and IR)].

The separation of the other compounds could not be effected as their R values are very close. The efforts for the separation and characterisation of the other triterpenes are in progress.

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Synthesis of 3,5-Dimethyl-1-naphthol*

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THE preparation of 3,5-dimethyl-1-naphthol from *o*-xylene after suitable modification of the sequence of reactions shown in Fig. 1 and reported earlier by Royals and Green² for the synthesis of 3,5-dimethyl-1-tetralone is described.

Experimental

*Diethyl (o-xyllyl) malonate*¹ (II): α -Bromo-*o*-xylene³ (I) (23.0 g; 0.12 M), b.p. 102°/15 mm; n_D^{30} 1.5746, obtained from *o*-xylene using N-bromosuccinimide as the brominating agent³ was treated with sodium

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salt of malonic acid ester⁴ prepared by the reaction of molecular sodium (2.87 g; 0.12 g atoms) and diethyl malonate (28.0 g; 0.17 M) in toluene (100 ml). The product was worked up in the usual way and fractionated to furnish diethyl (*o*-xylyl) malonate (II) as a colourless, mobile liquid, b.p. 154°/5 mm n_D^{27} 1.4864 (reported: 1.4905)⁴; ν_{max} (liq. film): 3000, 1770 (s); 1750, 1471, 1460, 1379, 1159, 1040, 862 and 757 cm^{-1} . PMR spectrum: CH_2-CH_3 [1.18 δ ; 6H t with $J = 7.5$ c/s]; methyl on an aromatic ring [2.3 δ ; 3H, S], $>CH_2-CH<$ [3.2-3.63 δ , 3H, m]; $OOCH_2-CH_3$ [4.01 δ , 4H, q, $J = 7.5$ c/s, $\delta_A-\delta_B = 12$ c/s].

Diethyl- α -Me (o-xylyl) malonate (III): Sodium hydride (3 g; 0.1 M) was mixed with II (10.6 g; 0.04 M) in dry toluene (100 ml) and refluxed when the solution was complete, methyl iodide (8.5 g; 0.06 M) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 12 hr, cooled, diluted with water (100 ml) and processed. The product obtained was fractionated to furnish Diethyl-Me(*o*-xylyl) malonate as a colourless mobile liquid, b.p. 167°/5 mm; n_D^{28} 1.4822, yield: 8.76 g (78%), ν_{max} (liq. film): 3012, 2941, 1754, 1471, 1460 (s); 1389, 1250, 1117, 1031, 952, 869, and 754 cm^{-1} . PMR spectrum: CH_2-CH_3 [1.18 δ , 6H, t with $J = 7.5$ c/s]; $>CH_2-CH-CH_3$ [1.23 δ , 3H, S]; methyl on an aromatic ring [2.3 δ , 3H, S]; $>CH_2-CH-CH_3$ [3.2-3.63 δ , 3H, m]; $OOCH_2-CH_3$ [4.01 δ , 4H, q, $J = 7.5$ c/s, $\delta_A-\delta_B = 12$ c/s].

*α -Me- β -(*o*-tylyl) propionic acid (IV)*: The product (III) was boiled with a solution of HCl (conc; 22.7 ml) in acetic acid (glacial; 16 ml) for 15 hr; diluted with

water (50 ml) and worked up as usual. The resulting residue was distilled to furnish α -Me- β -(*o*-tylyl) propionic acid, b.p. 154°/5 mm; n_D^{28} 1.5055; yield: 4.89 g (97%), ν_{max} (liq. film): 2950, 1720, 1475, 1250, 950 and 750 cm^{-1} . PMR spectrum: $CH-CH_3$ (1.12 δ , 3H, d with $J = 7$ c/s); methyl on an aromatic ring (2.3 δ , 3H, S); $>CH_2-CH<$ [2.46-3.2 δ , 3H, m]; aromatic protons (7.0 δ , 4H, S); $-COOH$ (11.26 δ , 1H, S) D_2O exchangeable (Found: C, 74.56; H, 8.26; $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$ requires: C, 74.13; H, 7.92%).

*β -Me-(*o*-tylyl) butyric acid⁵ (VIII)*: The homologation of the acid (IV) via the alcoholnitrile sequence was found more practical than the Arndt-Eistert reaction. 2-Me-3-(*o*-tylyl)-1-propanol (V) was first obtained by the $LiAlH_4$ reduction of (IV). The product (V), b.p. 101°-102°/1.5 mm was treated with PBr_3 and 2-Me-3-(*o*-tylyl)-1-bromopropane (VI), b.p. 110°/4 mm; n_D^{30} 1.4765; thus obtained was treated with KCN to give 2-Me-3-(*o*-tylyl)-1-cyanopropane (VII), b.p. 144°/6 mm, n_D^{30} 1.5132. The VII was then hydrolysed with KOH in ethylene glycol furnishing VIII, b.p. 146°/4 mm; n_D^{29} 1.5310. ν_{max} (liq. film): 2941, 1724, 1493, 1418, 1299, 1242, 1176, 943, 769 and 751 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 74.76; H, 8.4. $C_{12}H_{15}O_2$ requires: C, 74.22; H, 8.24%).

3:5-Dimethyl-1-tetralone⁵ (IX): The acid (VIII, 1.7 g, 0.008 M) was added to P_2O_5 (8.0 g) and heated for 2-25 hr and left overnight. The reaction mixture was worked up and the residue fractionated to give the ketone, b.p. 118°-20°/1.5 mm; m.p. 62.5°. (Reported²: 63°-64°); yield: 1.4 g (90%). ν_{max}^{neat} : 1695, 1613, 1471, 1389, 1302, 1263, 1127, 1053, 943, 869, 865, 815, 735 and 694 cm^{-1} . PMR spectrum; $-CH-CH_3$ (1.16 δ , 3H, d with $J = 7$ c/s); $-CH_3$ on

Reagent

- (1) $NaCH_2(COOEt)_2$, (2) CH_3I , NaH , (3) HCl , H_2O , (4) $LiAlH_4$, (5) PBr_3 , (6) KCN , $DMSO$,
(7) KOH , CH_2OH , (8) $SOCl_2$, CH_2N_2 ; Ag_2O , Na_2CO_3 , (9) PPA , (10) Pd/c .

Fig. 1. Synthesis of 3,5-dimethyl-1-naphthol.

an aromatic ring (2.28 δ , 3H, S); aromatic protons at C₆ and C₇ (7.2 δ , m, W.H. 22 c/s); aromatic proton at C₈ (7.7 δ , d with J = 7.5 c/s) which shows further allylic coupling with the proton at C₆ (J = 2.5 c/s). (Found: C, 82.60; H, 8.5. C₂₁H₁₄O requires: C, 82.72; H, 8.10%).

3 : 5-Dimethyl-1-Naphthol (X) : The tetralone (IX, 1.0 g, 0.006 M) was dehydrogenated with Pd/c (0.4 g) for 2 hr at 310°-20°. After the reaction was complete, the residue (800 mg) was extracted with ether. The ether extract was then thoroughly extracted with aqueous NaOH solution (10%). The alkaline extract was once washed with ether and then acidified by dilute HCl (10%). The acidified solution on extraction with ether and processing as usual gave crude naphthol, m.p. 82°-83°, yield: 290 mg (29%). The crude naphthol was purified by repeated sublimation and finally crystallised from p.e. (40°-50°) to give colourless crystals, m.p. 101°-102°; yield: 100 mg (10%) $\lambda_{max}^{Ethanol}$ 326 (sh), 313 (sh), 298 and 225 nm [log ϵ , 3.76, 4.00, 4.14 and 4.87]; ν_{max}^{KBr} : 3400, 1408, 1277, 1242, 1147, 1031, 885, 862, 847, 813, 806 and 757. PMR spectrum: Two Ar-CH₃ (2.43 and 2.6 δ , 3H, S, each) phenolic -OH (5.2 δ , 1H, exchangeable) and aromatic protons (6.5-7.86 δ , 5H, complex m). (Found: C, 83.28; H, 7.32. C₁₂H₁₂O requires: C, 83.69; H, 7.02%). It gave a picrate, m.p. 90°-91° and a TNB adduct, m.p. 116.5°. For TNB adduct (Found: N, 9.78. C₁₉H₁₅O₉N₃ requires: N, 9.79%).

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Reactions of Borazine

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BORAZINE trimers have been used as insecticides¹, fungicides, antiseptics², pesticides^{3,4}, plasticizers⁵, and polymer catalyst⁶. The borazine trimer of the type [5H, 12H, 19H, tris, (1,3,2 benzo diazaborolo)] borazine, has been prepared either by refluxing *o*-phenylenediamine and alkyl borates (methyl, ethyl, *iso*-propyl) with⁷ or without⁸ solvent or pyrolysing the complex^{9,10} obtained from the reaction of *o*-phenylenediamine and borontrichloride.

This is claimed to be thermally^{11,1} and hydrolytically stable^{7,12,13}. Gerrard and co-workers¹⁴ obtained from *o*-phenylenediamine and borontrichloride, an insoluble, and infusible polymer, non resistant to hydrolysis. Hohnstedt and Pellicciotto¹⁵ reported the formation of 2-chloroborobenzimidazole from *o*-phenylenediamine dihydrochloride and borontrichloride. Boron polymers¹⁶, obtained from boronalkyls and phenyl-*iso*-nitrile, remained unchanged even when refluxed with mineral acid or base.

The controversial reports about the interaction of *o*-phenylenediamine and borontrichloride^{14,15,17} and the hydrolytical stability of the polymer have prompted to undertake reinvestigations.

